

STYLISTIC FIGURES AS TOOLS FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' DISCOURSE COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *In this article the core of the discourse competence in the context of stylistic figures usage is discussed. Discourse competence proposes development of ability to use language effectively in social contexts, including the organization and coherence of ideas, and the application of pragmatic knowledge in oral and written speech. Stylistic figures are the means to help making the speech more expressive and persuasive. The proposed methodology of discourse competence development focus on stylistic and rhetoric devices mastering in the process of language learning to foster students' communicative competence. The described core of the discourse competence and instructional strategies give evidence about importance of teaching stylistic and rhetoric devices of communication.*

Keywords: *discourse competence, stylistic figures of speech, language tool, ways of teaching, strategies and activities.*

1. Introduction

In language education, discourse competence is increasingly seen as important for speech construction to be effective in communication. While teaching language we should develop discourse competence as an ability to organize and convey ideas meaningfully in conversations and texts. Discourse competence also involves understanding the subtleties of language use in different social contexts. One underexplored way to build this competence is through the deliberate use of stylistic figures of speech. That's why, the article is devoted to description of ways or instructional strategies for students' discourse competence development on the basis of using stylistic devices.

The potential of stylistic devices for development of discourse competence. Discourse competence is a crucial component of effective communication, encompassing not just grammatical knowledge but also the ability to use language appropriately in context (Makhkamova, 2019). At the same time, discourse competence involves the ability to organize and interpret language meaningfully across extended text or conversation, making it a fundamental skill in language learning. Integrating stylistic devices into discourse competence instruction enhances learners' engagement, critical thinking, and interpretative skills (Canale & Swang, 1980).

The key functional core of the discourse competence is seen in organizing ideas expressively and effectively in accordance with the context. Stylistic figures of speech, such as metaphors, similes, anaphoras, and hyperboles, are key tools that enrich language, make it more persuasive and expressive. So, stylistic figures of speech are creative language tools that can add depth and emotional resonance to communication. They are often employed in literature and other types of the discourse, including everyday conversations to enhance expressiveness. For example,

G.Lakoff & M. Johnson stress that we face the metaphors in everywhere, even the name of their book (1980) is formulated metaphorically.

Discourse competence refers to the ability to generate and comprehend spoken or written language in a coherent and contextually suitable manner. It encompasses the understanding of how language operates beyond the level of individual sentences, including how meaning is constructed within broader texts and interactions. Thus, the key elements of discourse competence include coherence, cohesion, appropriateness, and stylistic effectiveness.

In general, stylistic figures of speech enrich communication by adding layers of meaning, emotional depth, and nuance. Their functions include:

Creating Imagery: Metaphors and similes help clarify abstract ideas by creating vivid mental images.

Eliciting Emotions: Rhetorical questions and hyperbole can provoke strong emotional responses and stimulate contemplation.

Enhancing Memorability: Devices like alliteration and assonance make phrases more engaging and easier to recall.

Facilitating Persuasion: Techniques such as repetition and parallelism can strengthen arguments and persuade audiences effectively.

Thus, multifunctional nature of stylistic devices makes them as important means for effective and expressive discourse production. The future philologist, teacher, translator's talks should be distinguished by the abundance of stylistic techniques usage. Considering their multifunctionality in speech and the complexity of their expression, mastering stylistic techniques presents a certain difficulty, so let's move on to describing ways of teaching these stylistic devices.

2. Ways or instructional strategies for discourse competence development

Analysis of academic literature shows that teachers apply various approaches and methods of teaching stylistic devices. It is necessary to some methods which are well-documented in academic literature as effective for teaching stylistic devices. They are contextualized instruction, task-based learning, and collaborative activities.

The first one is **contextualized instruction**, which places stylistic devices within relevant, authentic language contexts, has proven effective in discourse competence development. Boers (2000) emphasizes that teaching figures of speech within specific genres-like political speeches or literary excerpts-allows students to see how these devices shape the tone, persuasion, and coherence of discourse. This approach engages students in authentic language practice, making it easier for them to transfer stylistic knowledge into their own communication. Besides, by the help of this method we can develop cultural aspect of discourse competence. For instance, Lazar (2004) suggests using culturally relevant materials to teach metaphor and irony, which can otherwise be challenging for non-native speakers. Her research illustrates that learners benefit from analyzing how stylistic devices are used in real-world communication, such as media news or advertisements. This method fosters a more profound comprehension of figurative language, contributing to a nuanced understanding of discourse.

The second method is **Task-Based learning (TBL)** that that encourage students to use stylistic devices to solve real-life communication problems. Research by Willis & Willis (2007) shows that TBL not only enhances discourse competence but also supports retention by requiring students to actively apply stylistic devices. In one task, for example, students might create a persuasive advertisement using hyperbole, personification, or other stylistic devices.

Thus, this strategy is effective because it places learners in situations where they must engage critically with language, experimenting with different stylistic techniques to achieve their communicative goals. Dornyei (2001) also supports this approach, because such tasks engage students in higher-order-thinking, which is critical for mastering discourse competence.

The third method is related to **Collaborative learning** that has been shown to significantly benefit the acquisition of discourse competence. By working together, students gain exposure to diverse perspectives and approaches, enhancing their understanding of how stylistic devices contribute to discourse coherence and meaning (Long & Porter, 1985). Activities like peer review or group discussions allow learners to experiment with rhetorical strategies (See: Perelman & Olbrechts-Tyteca, 1969) in a supportive environment, receiving immediate feedback from peers.

Swan & Lapkin (2000) stress that collaborative dialogue in second language learning facilitates noticing and promotes reflection, which are essential for mastering stylistic figures. Group analysis of speeches or poetry, for example, allows students to identify and discuss stylistic features, improving both their comprehension and production of complex discourse.

As we see, integrating stylistic devices into discourse competence instruction through contextualized learning, task-based learning, and collaborative activities offers students practical and reflective learning opportunities. These instructional strategies help students not only comprehend and apply rhetorical techniques but also develop higher-order discourse skills, as supported by the research of Boers (2000), Willis & Willis (2007), Long & Porter (1985). In our view, the combination of real-world applications and critical engagement makes these strategies effective for deepening students' discourse competence and enhancing their ability to use language in nuanced, effective ways.

Taking into consideration the mentioned experience we need to identify the other instructional strategies for effective development of discourse competence through learning stylistic devices.

1. Exploration of Stylistic Devices

Identification: Engage students in recognizing various figures of speech within different texts. This could involve reading comprehension tasks focused on literature, speeches, and advertisements.

Analytical Discussions: Encourage students to discuss how these figures contribute to the overall message and impact of the discourse, focusing on the author's intentions and the audience's reactions.

2. Creative Writing Assignments

Incorporation of Devices: Assign writing exercises that require students to use specific figures of speech. For instance, they might be tasked with crafting a descriptive paragraph that employs metaphors or writing a persuasive speech utilizing rhetorical questions and repetition.

Peer Feedback: Implement peer review sessions where students critique each other's use of stylistic devices, promoting collaborative learning.

3. Role-Playing and Performance Activities

Readings: Invite students to perform excerpts from plays or speeches that effectively use rhetorical devices, enhancing their expressive abilities and deepening their understanding of the devices' roles in spoken discourse.

Debates and Discussions: Organize debates that require students to articulate their positions using various rhetorical techniques, fostering critical thinking and dynamic responses.

4. Utilization of Multimedia Resources

Media Analysis: Use advertisements, film scripts, and social media content to identify and analyze the use of stylistic figures. This approach can make learning more engaging and relevant to students.

Interactive Platforms: Encourage students to create and share multimedia presentations that incorporate stylistic figures, promoting creativity and collaboration.

5. Feedback and Self-Reflection

Structured Feedback: Provide targeted feedback on students' use of rhetorical devices in their spoken and written outputs, highlighting strengths and suggesting areas for improvement.

Reflective Practice: Encourage students to reflect on their application of stylistic figures in their work through journals, allowing them to track their growth and understanding over time.

Thus, there are a variety of ways for development of discourse competence under the angle of stylistic devices or rhetoric patterns learning those help to make target speech more expressive, authentic and creative from language and stylistic points of view.

3. Conclusion

Enhancing discourse competence by examining and applying stylistic figures of speech significantly enriches language learning. By adopting targeted instructional strategies that encourage analysis, creativity, performance, and reflection, educators can foster the development of more skilled communicators who understand the nuanced impact of language. This approach not only improves students' linguistic and discourse production abilities but also equips them to manage the intricacies of authentic communication. The exploration of stylistic figures allows learners to deepen their understanding of discourse, ultimately enabling them to become more persuasive, perceptive, and eloquent speakers and writers.

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